

COMPETENCY APPROACH CONTENT IN TRAINING FUTURE TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract.

In this article, a scientific discussion was conducted about the practical and theoretical aspects of the competence approach in shaping the pedagogical characteristics of future technology teachers.

Keywords: Technological education, methodology, competence, problem situation, knowledge and skills, educational system.

In our country, all conditions and opportunities have been created for bringing up young people who are active, aspiring, talented and have high spiritual and moral qualities, who have acquired modern knowledge and professions - who are the decisive force of our today and tomorrow. Today, the development of science and technology requires a fundamental change in the requirements for education and its results. Based on this, the creation of new generation standards is an important task for pedagogues. The state education standards created until now were based on a systematic and active approach, that is, it consisted in clarifying the purpose of educational institutions in the way of mastering knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, it is required to define new state educational standards based on the competent-active approach aimed at self-development. Because the essence of the educational process organized in higher education is not to develop the needs and abilities of students, but to convey knowledge in an information-verbal way, to form skills and qualifications.

Information acquired in such a reproductive way does not allow the listener to develop practical experience. As a result, there are differences such as the fact that students accumulate a lot of information in vain, the effectiveness of education is low and it does not correspond to the real reality. More precisely, it seems that the student is far away from real life, and the goal is to learn only the previously collected information.

In order to eliminate the above urgent problems, it is considered appropriate to organize educational processes based on various new approaches. Our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "In order for our youth to become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on the world scale, our state should be happy. and we will mobilize all the forces and possibilities of our society", it is not without attention that the thoughts of our independent Uzbekistan are focused on forming free-thinking content. Therefore, it is one of the high tasks before us teachers to organize lessons based on modern approaches based on the demands of the new era.

The only way out of this problematic situation is to introduce a new, i.e. competent, approach to higher education. A competent approach requires the student to acquire knowledge and skills not separately, but as a whole. In connection with this demand, in turn,

the system of choosing teaching methods is also changing. The selection and practical application of teaching methods requires the improvement of competencies and functions that meet the requirements of the educational process.

The competent approach is a new pedagogical reality from the point of view of modernization of higher education. Within this approach, practical activity experience, competence and competence are considered as didactic units, and the traditional three elements of education (triad) - "knowledge - skill - competence" are divided into six units (sextet) - "knowledge - knowledge". Analysis in the form of "qualification - qualification - experience of practical activity - competence - competence" is required. First of all, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concept of "competence". Competence (a Latin word that means to reach, come right) is the readiness of the subject to set a goal and to effectively implement external and internal resources to achieve it, in other words, this subject's is a personal ability to successfully solve problems related to a specific object of activity. It should be noted that most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" are related to professional education and professional activity. However, since this concept has the description of innovation in connection with general secondary education, there is a special need to clarify its essence.

Competence is the Latin word "Competentia", the dictionary meaning of which in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "having experience". Competence is the ability to do something effectively, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of the work, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of specific work functions.

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. L.M. Mitina pedagogical competence means knowledge about the subject, teaching methodology and didactics, pedagogical communication skills and competence, as well as self-development, self-improvement, self-realization understood the harmonious combination of methods and means of improvement.

He distinguished the following three constituents in the structure of pedagogical competence: active, communicative and personal. Based on the structuring of pedagogical competence proposed by L.M. Mitina, we believe that the following set of competencies is sufficient and necessary, the level of acquisition of which determines the level of development of pedagogical competence for future specialists:

- ❖ *functional or special competence (knowledge, skills, qualifications and individual methods of pedagogical activity);*
- ❖ *personal or professional competence (knowledge, skills and abilities related to professional self-improvement and self-realization);*
- ❖ *communicative competence (knowledge, skills and competence related to the creative implementation of pedagogical activities).*

Concepts of professionalism and competence have common features. It should be noted that people who fully meet the established requirements and standards do not always become true professionals, because some do not know how to apply knowledge in practice, so such pedagogical activity remains ineffective.

It is appropriate to divide professional pedagogical competencies into separate types:

1. *special pedagogical competence;*
2. *to have enough information to carry out pedagogical activity at the necessary level.*

In addition, the pedagogue's ability to properly assess his professional level and determine his development as a specialist depends on this type:

- *social pedagogical competence;*
- *the level of social competence determines the pedagogue's ability to effectively build relationships with colleagues, plan joint actions.*
- *Effective communication skills, pedagogical culture and responsibility for work results;*
- *all these are included in the concept of social pedagogical competence;*
- *personal pedagogical competence;*
- *this is the ability to rationally organize pedagogical work, time management, striving for personal growth are its main components.*

Pedagogical-psychological training-seminar, work game, master class and involvement in various practical trainings, increasing the role of professional practice, creating favorable conditions for each student to demonstrate his/her pedagogical activities and skills social-perceptive competence can be formed through it. For this, it is necessary not only to master the knowledge, skills and abilities related to this field, but also to master the technique of establishing communication with people, to develop the motivational field, to increase psychological knowledge, and to psychologically prepare for professional activity.

The level of preparation for the demonstration of competence can be determined according to the following criteria: the idea of self-development and self-expression, preparation for making decisions about choosing a professional path, getting married, having children, readiness to respond to one's own life, independent choice of life path, readiness to form skills in the field of profession, etc.

In conclusion, it should be said that not only the direction of education to the learner, but also the teacher's psychological readiness for pedagogical activity is important in providing education and training to a person. In such cases, it is necessary to pay special attention to the level of professional competence of the teacher. Acceptance of the competent approach in the educational system as the conceptual basis of educational reforms, the introduction of the competent approach to the educational system is based on the educational goal, content, form of teaching, teaching methods, pedagogical and information technologies, control methods and requires making serious changes in the role of teacher and learner. In order to develop the professional competence of the teacher, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in pedagogical higher education. Higher education At the time when certain works are being carried out in the direction of improving the state educational standard, curriculum and textbooks, although it is difficult to abandon the existing traditional content, it is necessary to further clarify the content of education..

References:

1. Semina E.A. (2010). Competence model of a graduate of a pedagogical university - a future teacher of mathematics. Almanac of modern science and education. - No. 5 (36). - S. 133-135.

2. Muslimov N.A., Urazova M.B., Eshpulatov Sh.N. (2013). Technology for the formation of professional competence of vocational education teachers. - T.: Science and Technology Publishing House.
3. Mitina L.M. (2004). Psychology of work and professional development of the teacher. - M.: Academy. - 320 p.
4. Nodira Urishevna Asilbayeva Scientific-methodological bases of future technology education teacher training Vol. 3 No. 4 (2022): Science and Education;
5. Ghafarova T. and others. Advanced technologies of education.–Karshi Nasaf, 2003.
6. Shakhlo Kharratova “USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS” Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;

